

Planar Dual-Band ISM Antenna for Wireless Sensors

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Abstract— A planar dual-band circular antenna for a chemical wireless sensor network is described in this paper. Four antennas compose the wireless sensor package and one antenna is selected at a given time using an SP4T switch. This work describes the unit antenna used to transmit sensor information to a nearby hub that operates in the ISM bands. The antenna is composed of concentric shorted annular rings using substrate integrated waveguides and includes a circular patch at its center. The antenna presents two types of radiation patterns, one omni-directional in the azimuth plane at 2.4 GHz, and one uni-directional in the elevation plane at 5.8 GHz. The simulated gains obtained at 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz are 2 dB and 7 dB, respectively.

Keywords—ISM Band; SIW; dual-band; omnidirectional antenna; directional antenna; wireless sensor

I. INTRODUCTION

A planar dual-band antenna with multiband has the reliability and simplicity required to be integrated into chemical sensors heads, operating at infrared wavelengths [1], and respective optoelectronics in a package. ISM-band antennas are usually employed to undertake high quality data transmission using unlicensed bands.

In previous recent years, the substrate integrated waveguide (SIW) structure has been used for the production of high performance planar circuits [2]. SIW technology has a good and simple fabrication yield with planar form, resulting easy to integrate with other components, enabling RF circuits for high data transmission [3,4]. Several passive and active RF circuits have been proposed using SIW technology, among these circuits, are resonators, couplers, and antennas [5,6].

A loop-type antenna with dual-band omnidirectional patterns is presented in [7]. A compact design with two modes at a single resonance frequency with two input probe feeds for MIMO applications is shown in [8], this antenna is done in a complex multilayer structure and provides low gain. However,

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there are few ISM antennas with multiband and dual-mode characteristics simultaneously. In [9] a circular patch antenna with a bandwidth below 0.5 GHz for WiFi applications is proposed. The antenna structure is based on adding a set of conductive vias, this design has a gain of 6 dB with single-band operation.

In order to deploy a wireless sensor network for remote monitoring of chemical contamination, a dual-band antenna operating in the industrial, scientific and medical (ISM) frequency bands is designed, fabricated and measured. Section II describes the antenna design and parameters used in its implementation. The measurement and simulation results are presented in section III. Finally, section IV provides a conclusion for this work.

II. ISM ANTENNA FOR WIRELESS SENSORS

Fig. 1 shows the proposed antenna design. The design is based on previous work described in [10]. The antenna dimensions are presented in Table I. In this paper, an outer ring is added to the antenna with SIW via holes that allows obtaining a good impedance match and isolates port 1 from frequencies above 2.4 GHz. The outer antenna has two radius $R1$ and $R2$, with a slot width $w1$. The inner antenna has a radius corresponding to $R3$ in Fig.1 and resonates at 5.8 GHz. A Taconic RF-30 substrate is used to design the antenna, with a thickness $t = 1.52$ mm and a dielectric constant of 2.78.

Fig 2 shows the simulated comparison between the design in [10], labeled “without SIW outer ring” and the antenna described in this paper, which includes the SIW outer ring. It is apparent from Fig. 2 that the outer SIW ring added in this work improves potential interference mitigation from resonant frequencies over 2.4 GHz. Design theory for this antenna can be obtained in [10-13].

Table II shows the simulated comparison between the original design in [10] and this work using the same substrate, for the 2.4 GHz band. A slight increase in bandwidth and gain

can be obtained by adding the SIW outer ring to the design in [10].

In this paper, a single layer structure, two probe-fed, dual-band circular antenna using SIW cavities is described. One circular patch at the center of the antenna operates at 5.8 GHz. A short circuited annular ring slot antenna operates at 2.4GHz.

Fig. 1. Proposed antenna geometry (a) Top view without SIW cavity[10]; (b) Bottom view with SIW cavity (proposed antenna); (c) Side view.

TABLE I. ANTENNA DESIGN PARAMETERS IN MILLIMETERS

R_{siw}	$R1$	$R2$	$R3$		
39.42	32.12	16.1	8.2		
$p1$	$p2$	t	d	$w1$	
25.5	2.9	1.52	1	3	

III. ISM ANTENNA RESULTS

The proposed antenna is simulated using HFSS and CST commercial software, CST software is based on the integral method and HFSS is based on the finite element method (FEM). The two circular antennas in Fig.1 are well isolated using the SIW metalized vias. The TM_{10} mode current distribution at 2.4

GHz is concentrated around the outer antenna (see Fig.3a) and produces a quasi-omnidirectional pattern. The TM_{11} mode current distribution at the inner patch antenna (see Fig.3b) produces perpendicular radiation with respect to the planar antenna state.

Fig. 2. Comparison between the work in [10] (without SIW outer ring) and the antenna described in this work with the added SIW outer ring.

TABLE II. COMPARISON BETWEEN ANTENNAS FOR THE 2.4 GHz BAND.

	Bandwidth [MHz]	Gain [dB]
Antenna in [10]	48.7	1.73
Proposed antenna	56.3	2.11

Fig. 3. Current density (a) TM_{01} mode at 2.4 GHz, (b) TM_{11} mode at 5.8 GHz.

The antenna prototype is fabricated and measured after optimization performed through simulations. A photograph of the antenna top side is shown in Fig.4a, and Fig.4b shows the antenna bottom side.

Fig. 4. Photograph of the antenna prototype, (a) antenna top side, (b) antenna bottom side.

The simulated and measured reflection coefficient results are shown in Fig.5. The simulated and measured results are in good agreement, except for a slight frequency shift of the TM_{11} mode, which may be caused by the probe-feed position displacement after fabrication and by fabrication tolerances. The measured relative bandwidth for this antenna is around 89 MHz at 2.4 GHz and 220 MHz at 5.8 GHz, corresponding to 2.2% and 5.7% bandwidths at 2.4GHz and 5.8 GHz, respectively. A high isolation between the feeding probes is obtained by dividing the antennas using the SIW vias. Measurement and simulation results related to the isolation between ports is shown in Fig. 6. The isolation (transmission coefficient between ports 1 and 2) is below -26 dB, thus, the two antennas operate independently.

Fig. 5. Simulation and measured reflection coefficient of the antenna, (a) S_{11} for 2.4 GHz operation and (b) S_{22} for 5.8 GHz operation.

Antenna radiation patterns were measured in an anechoic chamber for the two antenna bands of operation. Fig. 7 shows the normalized radiation patterns corresponding to the 2.4 GHz band and Fig. 8 shows the radiation patterns corresponding to the 5.8 GHz band.

A good agreement between measurement and simulation is obtained regarding the radiation pattern results for the two antenna bands of operation, as shown in Figs. 7 and 8.

Fig. 6. Simulated and measured isolation between *port1* and *port2*.

Fig. 7. Simulated and measured radiation pattern of the antenna (a) E-field at 2.4 GHz; (b) H-field at 2.4 GHz.

Fig. 8 Simulated and measured radiation pattern of the antenna (a) E-field at 5.8 GHz; (b) H-field at 5.8 GHz.

IV. CONCLUSION

The paper proposed a dual-band two-port SIW cavity antenna. The antenna is composed of two independent antennas operating with different modes and effectively isolated using SIW metalized vias. The antenna resonant frequencies can be tuned independently for ISM dual-band operation. The planar

antenna structure and its performance make it a suitable candidate for integration with chemical sensor heads for wireless sensor networks.

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